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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Investigating Communication Strategies of the Federal Road Safety Commission (FRSC) and the Adoption of Safety Precautionary Measures among Commercial Drivers in Taraba State

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to assess the effectiveness of communication strategies employed by the Federal Road Safety Corps (FRSC) of Nigeria in influencing motorists' behaviour towards adopting various road safety measures. The study used a survey design that targeted commercial motorists at Jalingo Main Park, Taraba State, Nigeria. A sample of 118 respondents was selected using accidental sampling, with data collected through face-to-face questionnaires and was analyzed using descriptive statistics. The findings showed a significant exposure of motorists to a range of FRSC campaign messages that addressed issues such as speeding, seat belt usage, and drug driving. Predominantly, radio, television, and stickers were identified as the primary channels through which these messages were accessed. Also, it was revealed that, despite exposure to the road safety communication campaign messages, there has been a prevalently poor attitude among motorists towards adhering to safety measures, evident in behaviours such as over-speeding, overloading, and drug driving. Based on the findings, the study recommends the adoption wider communication channels including motor park outreaches and use of traditional and religious leaders to intensify campaigns tailored to cognitive patterns to positive behavioral change toward road safety precautionary measures among commercial motorists in Taraba State.

KEYWORDS

Communication, Strategies, Road, Safety, Commercial, Drivers

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Introduction

Road safety stands as a pressing global issue exacerbated by the frequent occurrence of traffic accidents, which annually claim an estimated 1.4 million lives and injure up to 50 million individuals worldwide (WHO, 2019). Despite Africa accounting for only approximately 2% of the world's vehicles, the continent bears a disproportionate burden, representing about 16% of global road fatalities (International Transport Forum, 2020). Nigeria, in particular, has faced significant challenges, recording 69,941 crashes and 35,179 fatalities between 2011 and 2016 alone (FRSC cited in Uhegbu & Tight, 2021), translating to an average of 16 road traffic fatalities daily. The consequences of these accidents extend beyond personal tragedy to encompass broader societal impacts. According to Aderamo (2012), economically, the loss of quality of life due to road accidents in Nigeria amounts to about 3% of gross national products.

In response to the challenges of road accidents, the Federal Government of Nigeria established the Federal Road Safety Commission (FRSC) under Decree No. 45 of 1988, subsequently amended by Decree 35 of 1992 and now known as the FRSC Act (CAP 141) Laws of the Federation of Nigeria (LFN) 1990 (Gana & Emmanuel, 2014). The FRSC is mandated not only to enforce traffic regulations and prosecute offenders but also to conduct public road safety education campaigns aimed at promoting voluntary adoption of safety measures among motorists. Tamara and Wigman (2011) argue that road safety campaigns, alongside enforcement measures and infrastructure improvements, constitute crucial strategies for addressing road traffic fatalities in any society.

The FRSC, through its Public Education and Enlightenment Department, invests significantly in communication activities such as media jingles, road safety posters, and recently established radio stations aimed at achieving its safety goals. However, the effectiveness of these communication strategies in influencing commercial drivers, particularly in Taraba State, remains underexplored. Similarly, there has been persistent road accidents linked to motorists' poor attitudes in the state (Shadrach, 2019), highlight potential shortcomings in the Commission's communication strategies. Therefore, this study sought to investigate the influence of FRSC communication strategies on influencing the adoption of road safety precautionary measures among commercial drivers in Taraba State.

This study uniquely examines the communication strategies utilized by the FRSC in Taraba State, focusing specifically on their influence on the safety behaviors of commercial drivers. This group is particularly significant as they are significantly involved in road traffic incidents in the state. By addressing this specific demographic, the study contributes to a deeper understanding of how targeted communication efforts can mitigate risk behaviors among high-impact groups, thereby enhancing overall road safety.

Objectives of the Study

The specific objectives of this study are:

1. To assess the level of exposure of commercial motorists in Nigeria to FRSC communication campaign messages.
2. To identify the communication channels through which commercial motorists in Nigeria access FRSC campaign messages.
3. To analyse the behaviour of commercial motorists in Nigeria regarding road safety precautionary measures communicated by the FRSC.

Literature Review

Communication Strategy

Effective communication is fundamental to the promotion of road safety. Similar to the strategic communication efforts employed by commercial organisations in advertising, public relations, and general marketing, the public health sector, including road safety, acknowledges the critical role of strategic communication in fostering safety. According to Ledru (1997), communication is of paramount importance in road safety campaigns. Prediger (1997) further asserts that communication is one of the essential tools for achieving a safe road traffic environment. However, without a meticulously defined communication strategy, even the most critical road safety messages may fail to achieve the desired impact, underscoring the necessity of strategic planning in communication efforts.

The concept of communication strategy encompasses the methods an organisation employs to convey messages to its target audience to achieve its objectives. Pattison (2011) describes it as a comprehensive planning approach that effectively engages audiences, while the Government Communication Service (2014) characterises it as a coherent narrative designed to solve communication challenges through strategic decision-making and resource allocation. Kibe (2014) further emphasises that a communication strategy articulates organisational goals and fosters a consistent voice, which is crucial for engaging stakeholders. Fundamentally, a communication strategy outlines the dissemination of information related to specific issues or events, guiding interactions with diverse audiences, including the public and stakeholders.

It aligns communication efforts with an organisation's mission, vision, and values (Albuali, 2021). Thus, communication strategy is a component of strategic communication that focuses on selecting effective communication channels to actualise organisational goals (Shadrach, 2021). However, communication strategies are not an end in themselves but a means to an end. This suggests that communication strategies may not fully address the unique challenges, particularly those faced by commercial drivers in Taraba State, in adopting road safety precautionary measures due to the distinct cognitive and behavioural patterns of these motorists. Therefore, it is imperative that a well-

structured communication strategy plan is designed to adequately address the cognitive and behavioural resistance to change in the target audience, which has developed over an extended period.

FRSC Communication Strategies

The Federal Road Safety Corps (FRSC), Nigeria's foremost government agency responsible for road traffic administration and safety management, employs a range of communication strategies to enhance public awareness of road safety. The FRSC extensively utilises electronic and print media, leveraging radio and television programmes to disseminate public enlightenment initiatives aimed at educating viewers and listeners on safety consciousness (Nnabuiife, Ekwenchi, & Ojiakor-Umenze, 2023). Additionally, newspapers provide a robust platform for sensitising the public to safer road usage, thereby contributing to efforts to reduce road traffic accidents. Safety jingles broadcast on radio and television further reinforce adherence to traffic regulations (Amah, Oladele, & Asemah, 2022).

In response to technological advancements, the FRSC has adopted new media approaches to effectively deliver road safety messages. Platforms such as Twitter, Facebook, YouTube, and other internet-based multimedia tools facilitate the rapid dissemination of information, fostering interactive engagement between message senders and receivers. This strategy enables real-time adjustments and responses to emerging trends in public enlightenment and road accident prevention campaigns (Mukhtar & Maidabino, 2020).

Workshops and seminars form a crucial component of the FRSC's communication strategy, bringing together stakeholders from the transport sector, policymakers, industry leaders, and educational communities. These events utilise presentations and slide shows to raise awareness of road safety measures, with the ultimate aim of reducing road traffic accidents (Nnabuiife, Ekwenchi, & Ojiakor-Umenze, 2023). Other strategies include direct engagement with commercial drivers through motor park rallies, where motorised processions further amplify safety messages along highways. Additionally, the FRSC employs advocacy advertising, which seeks to garner public endorsement and support for road safety initiatives. Unlike commercial advertising, advocacy efforts focus on influencing public attitudes and behaviours towards matters of public interest (Nwadinigwe, Osarenren, & Otuagoma, 2019). The FRSC also collaborates with traditional and religious leaders to engage and educate road users, particularly commercial motorists, on the importance of adhering to road safety regulations.

While the aforementioned communication strategies are critical in promoting road safety across Nigeria, it is important to recognise that commercial drivers in different regions of the country exhibit distinct cultural and behavioural patterns that may influence their response to FRSC messages. For instance, commercial motorists in Taraba State, who are deeply rooted in religious beliefs and long-standing

traditional practices regarding safety and protection, may not be uniformly influenced by the communication approaches generally adopted by the Commission. The implication is that for the FRSC to effectively influence road safety behaviours within different states, including Taraba State, their messaging and channel selection must be localised to resonate with the beliefs and literacy levels of commercial motorists.

Review of Empirical Studies

The review of empirical studies reveals several research efforts related to road safety and communication strategies, each offering insights into different aspects of public awareness and behavioural responses among drivers. Onuka and Akinyemi (2012) investigated the effectiveness of the Federal Road Safety Commission's (FRSC) public education programmes on drivers' road traffic habits in Lagos and Oyo States, Nigeria. Their findings underscored the positive impact of FRSC initiatives such as workshops, seminars, and media campaigns on improving drivers' behaviour, highlighting significant differences across different states in Nigeria. In contrast, Okafor, Odeyemi, and Dolapo (2013) focused on drivers' knowledge of specific road safety measures in Lagos, revealing substantial gaps in understanding among commercial minibus drivers. While their study highlighted deficiencies in driver knowledge regarding road signs and speed limits, it did not explore the role of communication strategies in enhancing awareness. Similarly, Okafor et al. (2014) assessed the effectiveness of post-license road safety education among minibus drivers in Lagos, noting improvements in knowledge but a limited impact on adherence to speed limits.

Furthermore, Ipinge and Owusu-Afriyie (2014) explored road safety programmes in Namibia, emphasising general awareness levels among road users but lacking an analysis of strategic communication management's influence on driver compliance with safety measures. Alonso et al. (2021) examined the recall of road safety campaigns in the Dominican Republic, highlighting low campaign recall rates and recommending targeted strategies for different demographic segments. Their findings underscore the importance of evaluating campaign effectiveness and targeting diverse audience groups, albeit outside the Nigerian context and without detailed exploration of communication strategies. Similarly, Ucheobi, Omego, and Ihejirika (2021) assessed awareness and compliance with the installation of speed-limiting devices among commercial drivers in South-South Nigeria, highlighting the effectiveness of face-to-face interactions and radio campaigns in conveying FRSC messages. Their study emphasised the role of diverse communication channels in enhancing driver awareness and regulatory compliance. Lastly, Ngene and Anorue (2021) examined motorists' exposure to the FRSC's "Don't Drink and Drive" campaign in Southeast Nigeria, revealing significant demographic variations in campaign impact and highlighting the campaign's role in influencing driver behaviour regarding alcohol consumption while driving.

In a related study, Nwadinigwe, Osarenren, and Otuagoma (2019) examined commercial drivers' perceptions of the Federal Road Safety Commission's (FRSC) education on compliance with road traffic rules and regulations in Delta State. Their study found that road traffic safety education programs had a positive influence on drivers' compliance with these regulations. They also found that drivers' personal experiences significantly impacted their adherence to road traffic rules. Similarly, Amah, Oladele, and Asemah (2022) investigated the impact of the Federal Road Safety Corps (FRSC) campaigns on motorists during the ember months in Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria. They discovered that a considerable portion of motorists (45%) had low exposure to the FRSC Ember Month Campaign. Television was identified as the primary channel through which motorists accessed the campaign, and the effectiveness of the campaign was perceived to be inadequate by many respondents.

Overall, while these studies contribute valuable insights into road safety and drivers' behaviours, gaps persist in comprehensively exploring the strategic elements of communication campaigns and the attitudes of commercial drivers, especially in the northern region of Nigeria, where there seems to be a dearth of studies on the subject matter. Therefore, this review underscores the need for further research to fill these gaps and enhance the effectiveness of road safety communication strategies in Nigeria.

Theoretical Framework

The communication-persuasion theory, developed by McGuire in 1976, integrates Lasswell's communication model by analysing the components of "who says what, in which channels, to whom, and with what effects. This theory not only explores the creation, transmission, reception, and assimilation of messages, but also considers external and internal factors such as individual attitudes, beliefs, and demographic characteristics like age and ethnicity that influence communication dynamics (Orina, 2014). In public health communication, this theory has been instrumental. Corcoran (2007) describes it as an input-output matrix where 'input' factors encompass five stages: source, message, channel, receiver, and destination. These input variables provide communication practitioners with options for selection and manipulation to achieve desired outcomes. The 'output' variables, as outlined by McGuire (2001) and cited in Orina (2014), delineate a sequence of events necessary for effective communication: exposure to the message, attention to the message, interest in the message, understanding of the message, cognitive processing, acquisition of necessary skills, agreement with the message, memory retention, message retrieval, decision-making based on the message, action performance, integration of action into behaviour, and advocacy to others to adopt similar behaviour.

McGuire posits that completing all these stages is essential to achieving the final stages of behavioural change and cognitive integration post-action (McGuire, 2001, cited in Orina, 2014). This systematic approach facilitates strategic communication

planning, enabling practitioners to systematically engage audiences and achieve behaviour change objectives. For instance, the Federal Road Safety Corps (FRSC) can leverage this theory to design road safety communication initiatives tailored to induce desired behavioural changes within society. By emphasising each stage of the communication process, this theory assists FRSC communication managers in identifying effective channels and strategies that influence campaign outcomes. This structured approach ensures that each message stage is critically evaluated for impact, appropriateness, and effectiveness, thereby optimising the overall effectiveness of road safety communication campaigns.

Research Methodology

The study employed a descriptive survey research design, selected for its capacity to generate comprehensive data from a small sample across a broad geographic area, enabling comparisons and generalisations across populations. Specifically, this design was used to evaluate the effectiveness of FRSC communication strategies among commercial motorists at Jalingo Main Park. To mitigate response bias inherent in survey research, participants were assured of confidentiality and anonymity, which encouraged honest responses and thereby ensured the integrity of the findings.

A sample size of 118 respondents was chosen using the accidental sampling technique. Accidental sampling was employed due to the challenge of accessing a complete list of commercial drivers at Jalingo Main Park, making it a practical approach for quickly gathering a representative sample. Data collection was conducted using a closed-item questionnaire administered face-to-face. This method of administration enhanced the validity and reliability of the data by allowing respondents to seek clarification on ambiguous or confusing questions, ensuring a full understanding and reducing the risk of misinterpretation, which increased the accuracy of their responses.

The validity of the instrument was ensured through content validity, with questionnaire items aligned to study objectives and assessed by experts. Reliability was confirmed with a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of $\alpha = 0.8311$, indicating high consistency in responses. Data analysis was conducted using descriptive statistics, specifically frequencies and percentages, to summarise the characteristics of the study population.

Data Presentation

Table 1: Respondents Demographic Data

Responses	Frequency N=118	Percentage 100%
<i>Age Range</i>		
21 - 30	21	17.8
31 - 40	39	33.1
41 - 50	25	21.2

51 - above	33	27.9
Marital Status		
Single	49	41.5
Married	69	58.5
Educational Qualification		
None	38	32.2
Primary Edu.	21	17.8
Secondary	39	33.1
Tertiary	20	16.9
Years of Driving		
1-5 years	49	41.5
6- 10 years	23	19.5
11 - 15 years	27	22.9
16-20 years	19	16.1
21 years and above	0	0

The data in the table above revealed that respondents were predominantly aged between 31 and 50 years, with 33.1% falling in the 31–40 age range and 27.9% aged 51 years and older. Marital status indicated a majority of married individuals (58.5%) compared to single respondents (41.5%). Regarding educational qualifications, the distribution was varied, with 32.2% having no formal education, 17.8% completing primary education, 33.1% attaining secondary education, and 16.9% having tertiary education. In terms of driving experience, the majority of respondents (41.5%) reported having driven for 1–5 years, followed by 22.9% with 11–15 years of experience and 19.5% with 6–10 years. Notably, none of the respondents reported driving for 21 years or more. These demographic and experiential characteristics provide a foundational understanding of the study population, which is crucial for interpreting their perceptions and behaviours related to road safety initiatives and adherence to traffic regulations.

Table 2: Respondents Exposure to FRSC campaign Messages

Responses	Frequency (N=118)		Percentage (100%)	
	Yes	No	Yes	No
Have you ever seen or heard an FRSC campaign message against speeding?	109 (92.4%)	9 (7.6%)		
Have you ever seen or heard FRSC campaign message about the use of seatbelt?	112 (94.9%)	6 (5.1%)		
Have you ever seen or heard FRSC campaign message about proper use of tyres?	48 (40.6%)	70 (59.3%)		
Have you ever seen or heard an FRSC campaign message discouraging drug driving?	115 (97.5%)	3(2.5%)		
Have you ever seen or heard an FRSC campaign message about road signs or codes?	51(43.2%)	67 (56.8%)		

Have you ever seen or heard an FRSC campaign message discouraging night driving?	39 (33.5%)	79 (66.9%)
Have you ever seen or heard an FRSC campaign message about registering your vehicle and obtaining a driving licence?	111 (94.1%)	7 (5.9%)
Have you ever seen or heard an FRSC campaign message against the use of mobile phones while driving?	109 (92.4%)	9 (7.6%)

Table 2 presents an analysis of respondents' exposure to various Federal Road Safety Corps (FRSC) campaign messages about road safety. The findings reveal a high level of awareness among respondents across most communication messages. Specifically, campaigns against speed driving and drug driving were widely recognised, with 92.4% and 97.5% of respondents acknowledging exposure to these messages, respectively. Similarly, messages promoting the use of seatbelts and registering vehicles with driving licenses were well-received, with 94.9% and 94.1% of respondents indicating awareness, respectively. Conversely, awareness levels were lower for certain messages. Campaigns addressing proper tyre use were less effective, reaching only 40.6% of respondents. Similarly, messages about road signs or codes and the dangers of night driving had lower levels of exposure, with 43.2% and 33.5% of respondents, respectively, indicating awareness. The campaign against using mobile phones while driving also showed moderate awareness (92.4%).

Table 3: Channels through which respondents accessed FRSC communication campaign messages.

Responses	Frequency (N=118)		Percentage (100%)	
	Yes	No	Yes	No
Radio	100 (84.7%)	18 (15.25%)		
Television	74 (62.7%)	44(37.3%)		
Billboard	49 (41.5%)	69 (58.47%)		
Stickers	72 (61%)	46 (38.9%)		
Newspaper/magazine	21(17.8%)	97 (82.20%)		
Social media	9 (7.6%)	109 (92.7%)		
Workshop and seminars	49 (41.5%)	69 (58.5%)		
Posters and handbills	46 (38.9%)	72 (61.01%)		
Motor Park and Motorized Rallies	55 (56.6%)	63 (53.4%)		
Religious gathering at Churches or Mosques	34 (28.8%)	84 (71.8%)		

The table presents a detailed overview of the channels through which respondents accessed communication campaign messages by the Federal Road Safety Corps (FRSC). Radio emerged as the most effective channel, with 84.7% of respondents reporting exposure to FRSC messages through this medium. Television followed closely behind, reaching 62.7% of respondents. These

findings underscore the significant reach and impact of traditional broadcast media in disseminating road safety information among commercial motorists. In contrast, billboard advertisements and stickers were accessed by 41.5% and 61% of respondents, respectively, highlighting their moderate effectiveness in conveying FRSC messages. Newspapers and magazines, however, demonstrated lower reach, with only 17.8% of respondents indicating exposure through print media. Similarly, social media platforms proved less effective, reaching only 7.6% of respondents, suggesting a need for enhanced digital communication strategies tailored to this audience. Workshops and seminars, along with posters and handbills, were accessed by 41.5% and 38.9% of respondents, respectively. These channels, which involve direct engagement and visual aids, appear to play a significant role in reinforcing FRSC messages. Motor park rallies and religious gatherings at churches or mosques also demonstrated moderate effectiveness, reaching 56.6% and 28.8% of respondents, respectively.

Table 4: Respondents' Behaviour to road safety precautionary measures communicated by FRSC.

Variables	Frequency (N=118)	Percentage (100%)
	Yes	No
I consume substances such as alcohol and drugs to stay alert while driving.	81 (68.6%)	37 (31.4%)
I refrain from making or answering calls while driving.	31 (26.3%)	87 (73.7%)
I enjoy driving at night.	60 (50.8%)	58 (49.2%)
I enjoy driving at high speeds.	93 (78.8%)	25 (21.2%)
I always wear a seat belt while driving.	41 (34.7%)	77 (65.3%)
I check my tyres before I start driving.	59 (50%)	59 (50%)
My vehicle is properly registered.	69 (58.5%)	49 (41.5%)
My driving license has expired.	68 (57.6%)	50 (42.4%)
I often disregard road signs or codes while driving.	70 (59.3%)	48 (40.7%)
I consistently overload my vehicle.	60 (50.8%)	58 (49.2%)

Table 4 provides insights into respondents' behavior in relation to road safety precautionary measures communicated by the Federal Road Safety Corps (FRSC). The findings reveal a mixed response in terms of adherence to safety practices among commercial motorists. A significant proportion, 68.6%, admitted to taking substances like alcohol and drugs to stay awake while driving, highlighting a concerning behaviour that poses risks to road safety. In contrast, only 26.3% of respondents reported refraining from making or answering calls while driving, indicating a lower adherence to this safety guideline.

Regarding specific driving preferences, 50.8% of respondents expressed a preference for driving at night, while 78.8% admitted to enjoying driving at high speeds. Conversely, compliance with wearing seat belts was relatively low, with only 34.7% consistently using seat belts while driving. Checking tyres before driving was a balanced response, with 50% of respondents indicating this practice. In terms of vehicle and documentation compliance, 58.5% confirmed that their vehicles were duly registered, whereas 57.6% acknowledged that their driving licenses had expired, highlighting a significant area of non-compliance. Additionally, a notable 59.3% admitted to disregarding road signs or codes while driving, and an equal percentage engaged in overloading, indicating prevalent risky driving behaviours among the respondents.

Discussion of Major Findings

This study investigated the exposure of commercial motorists at Jalingo Main Motor Park in northeast Nigeria to various road safety campaign messages, their preferred channels of exposure, and their behavioural responses to these messages. The findings reveal that a significant majority of the respondents were aware of key FRSC campaign messages, particularly those addressing drug driving (97.9%), speeding (94.9%), the use of seat belts (92.4%), and the prohibition of mobile phone use while driving (92.4%). This contradicts the findings of Ngene and Anorue (2021), who suggested that despite extensive road safety campaigns by authorities like the FRSC, Nigerian motorists remained largely uninformed due to the inadequate reach of campaign messages to the target audience. The heightened awareness of messages concerning drug driving and speeding may be attributed to the frequent occurrence and severe consequences of these behaviours in road traffic incidents, making them more prominent in public safety campaigns. Additionally, these issues are likely emphasised due to their direct impact on the safety of both drivers and passengers, thereby reinforcing their prevalence in the consciousness of commercial motorists.

Moreover, the study revealed significant gaps in exposure to messages related to tyre use (40.6%), road signs or codes (43.2%), and night driving (33.5%), aligning with Shadrach's (2019) critique that FRSC campaigns historically neglected critical issues such as tyre safety. Ipinje and Owusu-Afriyie (2014) also noted that while popular, road safety campaigns often overlooked comprehensive road safety themes beyond the traditional focus on drug driving, seat belt use, and mobile phone usage. Tyre safety and night driving receive less attention in Nigerian road safety campaigns likely because they are perceived as secondary concerns compared to more immediate and high-risk behaviours like drug driving and speeding. Additionally, there may be less awareness of the importance of tyre maintenance and cautious night driving. These topics may be considered less engaging and harder to communicate effectively, resulting in their relative neglect in public safety messaging, especially

when resources are directed towards addressing more prominent and easily understood dangers.

The study further identified radio (84.7%), television (62.7%), stickers (61%, and rallies as the primary channels through which respondents accessed road safety campaign messages. This finding corroborates previous research (e.g Anorue, 2021; Oladele & Asemah, 2022; Onuka and Akinyemi, 2012; Ucheobi, Omego, & Ihejirika, 2021 etc) highlighting the prevalent use of traditional media channels in FRSC's communication strategies. The popularity of radio, television, and stickers as primary channels for accessing road safety campaign messages can be attributed to their widespread reach, accessibility, and effectiveness in engaging diverse audiences. Specifically, Radio has an extensive coverage and ability to reach even remote areas, its popularity is further bolstered by the fact that radio broadcasts can be easily integrated into daily routines, allowing drivers to stay informed while on the move.

Furthermore, the study revealed that respondents displayed inadequate attitudes towards road safety precautionary messages, engaging in risky behaviours such as drug driving, speeding, and using mobile phones while driving. These actions significantly jeopardise their safety and that of their passengers. This finding corroborates previous research in Nigeria, which highlights a pervasive disregard for road safety guidelines among motorists. Atubi and Gbadamosi (2015) attributed the high accident rates on Nigerian roads to motorists prioritising profit over safety, resulting in reckless driving habits, insufficient vehicle maintenance, and extended nighttime driving. Similarly, Onuka and Akinyemi (2012) observed that motorists frequently ignored safety measures and resorted to bribery to avoid penalties when apprehended by road officials. The poor non-compliance with road safety regulations among commercial motorists in taraba State can be attributed to diverse factors which include economic motivations, inadequate enforcement and systemic corruption.

Conclusion

This study examined the exposure of commercial motorists at Jalingo Main Motor Park in northeast Nigeria to various road safety campaign messages, their preferred channels of exposure, and their behavioural responses. The findings reveal a high level of awareness regarding key road safety messages, particularly those addressing drug driving, speeding, seat belt use, and the prohibition of mobile phone use while driving. Nonetheless, there were significant gaps in the exposure to messages related to tyre safety, road signs or codes, and night driving. The study also highlighted that radio, television, and stickers are the primary channels through which respondents accessed road safety messages. Additionally, the study found that respondents displayed poor attitudes towards road safety messages, engaging in risky behaviours such as drug driving, speeding, and using mobile phones while driving, thereby endangering their own safety and that of their passengers. This finding underscores a pervasive disregard for road safety

guidelines, influenced by factors such as economic motivations, inadequate enforcement, and systemic corruption.

The study emphasises the need for targeted interventions to address the poor attitude of commercial motorists in Taraba State. Future research should focus on developing strategies to enhance compliance among commercial motorists with road safety measures and investigate the underlying factors contributing to non-compliance, such as economic pressures and enforcement challenges. Such research could provide valuable insights to inform policy and practice in road safety.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions drawn from the study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Given the prevalence of poor road safety behaviour among commercial motorists in Taraba State despite high exposure to FRSC messages, it is essential to develop targeted campaigns that consider the cognitive patterns of drivers.
2. Since road safety communication campaigns in Taraba State often focus on issues such as speeding, drunk driving, and seat belt use, while neglecting topics like tyre safety, road signs, and night driving, there is a critical need for the FRSC to enhance campaigns by incorporating these neglected issues. These areas should receive increased visibility and emphasis within road safety communication initiatives.
3. Considering that FRSC communication campaigns in Taraba State predominantly use traditional media such as radio and television, there should be a concerted effort to utilize interpersonal communication channels such as rallies, workshops, and seminars. These platforms can facilitate direct engagement with drivers, fostering a better understanding and acceptance of road safety messages.
4. To encourage commercial motorists in Taraba State to adopt safety precautionary measures, it is necessary to collaborate with opinion leaders, including religious leaders and leaders of the National Union of Road Transport Workers (NURTW). Leveraging their authority and broad influence can significantly amplify the reach and impact of road safety campaigns.

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